

NATIONAL CARBON-CREDIT COOPERATIVE-BANK (NCCB) FOR INDIAN GREEN- ECONOMY

Dr. Rudranarayan Mohapatra,
Senior Technical Officer, C-DAC, Pune, 411007
dr.rudranarayan@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Carbon markets have been a key driver of channelling finance and investment to projects to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in developing countries like India since the Kyoto Protocol came into effect. And the carbon credits contribute to meeting the incremental costs of green investments to become a key component of the IFC climate business strategy. The weaknesses of cap-and-trade systems, governance issues arise as it cut across traditional institutional boundaries and always inspires for an independent governing body, in the form of a National Carbon-credit Co-operative Bank (NCCB), which would principally be charged with price management, thereby increasing the confidence in the system of both investors and covered entities. The proposed institutional management system would help to tackle market expectations and investor activity driven by exogenous factors such as weather conditions, fuel prices and the general level of economic activity. In addition to, the proposed NCCB would play a role – either directly or indirectly – in shaping market design issues that are within the purview of the policy and political realm to provide a greater degree of stability in the overall policy to country like India.

KEY WORDS: National Carbon-Credit Cooperative-Bank (NCCB), Green Economy, International Emission Trading (IET), certified emission reductions (CERs)

1. INTRODUCTION

National Carbon-Credit Cooperative-Bank (NCCB) is being conceptualized as an initiative that encourages, supports, and enhances community-based indigenous forestry and energy saving through carbon credit trading to enable successful climate change adaptation, socio-economic development for local communities and biodiversity conservation in India's upcoming smart-villages. The aim of this establishment in India is to positively impact villages in rural India under *International Emission Trading (IET) framework*. Each village will establish a community forest, in return for this each village gains access to income generating loans via a micro-finance system Unlike NABARD or other cooperative organization. However as a pilot base mode looking to the necessity, the system would at first target 2 cities of India and their peripheral villages. The revenue generated from the bank is directed back to the community to allow infrastructure development within the smart-village for future development.

2. BACKGROUND:

Carbon credits are certificates issued to countries that reduce their emission of GHG (greenhouse gases) which causes global warming. Carbon credits are measured in units of certified emission reductions (CERs). Each CER is equivalent to one of carbon dioxide reduction. Under IET (International Emissions Trading) mechanism, countries can trade in the international carbon credit market. Countries with surplus credits can sell the same to countries with quantified emission limitation and reduction commitments under the Kyoto Protocol. Developed countries that have exceeded the levels can either cut down emissions, or borrow or buy carbon credits from developing countries.

CARBON CREDITS are generated by enterprises in the developing world that shift to cleaner technologies and thereby save on energy consumption, consequently reducing their greenhouse gas emissions. For each one of carbon dioxide (the major Green house gases) emission avoided, the entity can get a carbon emission certificate which they can sell either immediately or through a futures market, just like any other commodity. The certificates are sold to entities in rich countries, like power utilities, which have emission reduction targets to achieve and find it cheaper to buy 'offsetting' certificates rather than do a clean-up in their own backyard. This trade is carried out under UN-mandated international convention on climate change to help rich countries reduce their emissions.

The credit carbon mechanism was formalized in the Kyoto protocol, an international agreement between more than 170 countries, and the market mechanisms were agreed through the subsequent Marrakesh Accords. The main aim of this agreement is to reduce the carbon emission in the global atmosphere to balance the natural environment.

The IT Vision of Reserve Bank India - 2011-17 on the issue of "Augment Green Credentials" traced upon "Leveraging on the benefits of lower-power, more energy-efficient devices and architecture can lead to tangible savings in energy costs and help to lend build 'green'

credentials to IT. Shifting to more efficient products and practices can allow for more equipment to fit within an energy footprint, or to fit into a previously filled centre. IT can enable many green initiatives. Converting to online and mobile banking helps the environment. To manage carbon footprints and achieve the objective of becoming environmental friendly, it is important to implement Workflow Management Systems (WMS) using the concept of 'less paper office'.¹

Though some active players like 'Carbon Clear Limited' at UK, 'Plant a Tree Today Foundation' A UK registered charity and a Thailand Foundation in international level and 'Carbon Clear India' New Delhi, IDBI Bank of India are in national level playing pivotal role but their role at present limited to Industrial business Purpose and have hardly any mechanism to share credit with ground level stakeholders.

At present irrespective of a developing nation, India is heading towards a developed nation by growing its socio-Economic as well as the infrastructural development. Though some measures are being taken by some private Organizations in this direction but not sufficient to make this noble goal fulfil. And no such effective awareness programme lunch to involve the grass root stakeholders to get the benefit. For the said purpose here is the concept of NCCB and its effective management system to educate and involve every citizen of our country for future business as well as sustainable environment.

3. NCCB COPE & OBJECTIVE:

The objectives of proposed concept are including, but not limited to:

- Inspiring Govt to make a parallel policy inside our country under the framework of IET in a pilot mode till to achieve a better emissions trading scheme.
- Establishing a National Carbon-Credit Cooperative-Bank inside the country that could function in the mission of IET framework.
- Establishing Green-data Centre in local village level.
- Provide information for Native Forest Restoration for Smart- Villages
- Cooperate for Environmental Education in Local languages
- Helps is Community Development
- Establishing a harmonious carbon Credit-business environment inside the country.

4. BENEFITS TO GROUND LEVEL STAKEHOLDERS FROM NCCB:

- Issuing Green-Carbon Card to direct initiators for planting 100 trees (or any quantified number) each year and nurturing for certain years to same trees.
- Provide social upliftment facility for individual and their families as a Green-Carbon Card holder.
- Tackling the social problems and environmental issues to strengthen financially by the addition of saleable carbon credits.

¹ IT VISION OF RESERVE BANK OF INDIA 2011-2017, Page No 11,
<http://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/PublicationReport/PDFs/ITVSD220211.pdf>

- To make a bridge between Smart-village to Smart-city the business of exchange between Carbon Credit Capital and other Materialistic Capital.

5. COMMERCIAL ADVANTAGE THROUGH NCCB :

An effective Carbon-Credit Co-operative Banking will deliver definite economic return to the involved organizations and also helps for:

- Reducing your carbon footprint will support both environmental and financial goals.
- Low Carbon Credentials will help for Protecting Image Brand.
- Differentiate from Other Competitors in a business environment and quality control.
- Win New Business using Supply Chain records and including environmental record during procurement decisions.

6. COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF ESTABLISHING NCCB IN INDIA:

Movements toward greening the global economy and decoupling resource use from economic growth present new opportunities for Indian economies. As the nation arguably most affected by climate change, it is heartening to see that there is an opportunity, by tapping into India's abundant natural/renewable sources for more sustainable energy, to derive economic and developmental benefit from the global drivers behind it. By placing a market value on activities that can reduce GHG emissions, the carbon market is increasingly being used as a tool to finance this transformation.

STRENGTHS:

- Following a promising bilateral summit between India and USA in September 2014, the two countries prioritized advancing climate action and clean energy.
- The new elected government of India has also announced a \$100 billion investment in India's renewable energy sector over the next few years to help meet ambitious new clean energy targets.
- RBI's Green Banking Framework publication is comparatively a new development in the financial world.
- According to Climate Action Tracker report, India on the Copenhagen Accord on 30 January 2010 pledged to reduce the emission intensity of its GDP by 20 to 25% by 2020 compared to 2005 levels.
- According to India Green Building Council, "Green Building Movement in India," The country has dramatically increased its registered green floor area from just 20,000 square feet in 2004 to 2.59 billion square feet as of November 2014, with 562 certified projects and 2,847 registered projects.

WEAKNESS:

- High Population growth and India is a developing nation
- The polluting industries are not effectively using the GHG reduction techniques for their Greenhouse Gas emissions.
- For polluting industries, It is cheaper to pollute and buy credits than it is to change their production processes.

- Negligent verification for carbon-offset projects
- Carbon-Credit Trading and its benefits not reaching to mass people.
- Carbon-Credit trading is highly dependable on climate and regulatory zone.
- Volunteering needed by citizens.
- Creating Awareness among citizens and issue of policy framing.
- Despite its popularity among advocates of market solutions to global warming, carbon trading has not yet produce the quantitative and qualitative changes that the nation needs.

OPPORTUNITIES:

- No such kind of Co-operative bank is established in national level to attach common people for Carbon-credit business.
- Government looking to have Public Private Partnerships in development.
- This is the first of its kind initiative to support eco-friendly and green initiatives across the country.
- The system and institution would reinforces the message, that spending wisely and responsibly is a great way for our customers/citizens to reap the benefits of using their Carbon-Credit right to support environmental initiatives in India.
- With the help of technology technological, available optimization of recourses can be done.
- Government is looking to develop 100 smart cities and number of smart villages with sustainable eco-friendly environment in India.
- To understand the carbon impact of common mans event, like energy use in leaving room, cooking, meeting spaces, travel to and from the event (including flights, driving, and transportation throughout the duration of the event) etc. Measuring these aspects can reveal opportunities for lower-carbon alternatives.
- In future the common mans saving and lifestyle will be regulated by carbon footprint.
- India's smart cities can be converted to cool cities by this initiative.
- Greening Use of Laptops, Desktop Computers, and Servers across the banks but no such common Auditing agencies yet to be established for its ensure.
- The NCCB can encourage the common people to profit from efficiencies and nurture would be a right for them.

THREATS:

The measures adopted by others in response to the threat of climate change — whether international, national, or local in origin — range from international treaties such as the Kyoto Protocol, to market measures such as increases in insurance premiums, to national government regulations forcing businesses to reduce their emissions of GHGs. Looking this following threats can be considered:

- A very diversity in long-term rainfall levels, climatic instability etc.
- Carbon trading is a source of windfall profits for polluting sectors.
- Carbon trading is a new source of social inequality, and thus of potential social unrest that could thwart the climate change mitigation policy.

The allocation of emission rights amounts to an unprecedented distribution of property rights in the carbon cycle and its regulation may be socially and geographically unfair.

7. FOSTERING NCCB IN INDIA

The NCCB would be intended to manage flow of: 1) Information on changes in forest carbon stocks between levels, 2) Incentives to carbon rights holders. The system not would just be charged with price management, but also perform a variety of market oversight and management functions, including:

- Carbon Footprint Measurement to deliver standards compliant carbon footprint and its reduction.
- Professional forecasting and judgments about the consequences of different outcomes with regards to emissions and carbon prices etc
- Allocating allowances, tracking offset ownership, and conducting auctions.
- Monitoring emissions and assessing progress towards emissions reduction.
- Managing cost-containment mechanisms, buying and selling allowances, approving offset projects, etc.
- Coordination with various government bodies

So an overall fostering of NCCB can be represented from **Fig No 1**

Fig. No. 1

8. EXPECTED OUTCOMES & OUTPUTS FROM NCCB:

According to 'The Reuters', on Jan 25, 2015, on subject 'Obama backs India's solar goals, seeks support for climate talks' The Hon'ble President of USA, Mr. Obama said in a joint press conference with Prime Minister of India on the first day of his three-day visit to New Delhi, "We very much support India's ambitious goal for solar energy, and stand ready to speed this expansion with additional financing". Again "The prime minister and I made a personal commitment to work together to pursue a strong global climate agreement in Paris,"

Obama said. "As I indicated to him, I think India's voice is very important on this issue."² During that conference, 196 nations are expected to meet and tentatively agree a course of action to respond to climate change. It is widely considered the last chance for a global agreement that could feasibly keep the rise in global average temperatures under 2°C.

Co-operative Bank would be the key instrument in developing countries like India to contribute to ecological footprint directly and indirectly through investment/lending in their customer enterprises. As such the proposed system would play a pivotal role in optimizing /reducing the carbon footprint.

In the outcome, the establishment would consider the recommended metrics by Green Grid or other recommended organizations to measure the effectiveness of green initiatives in information technology and data centres. Some of the important metrics for the system outcomes are: Energy disposal efficiency, Carbon Usage effectiveness and other data centre productivity to create a suitable business market for NATURE CAPITAL.

With this the proposed systems outputs are:

- Comparable competency eco-friendly environment.
- Economic savings for households reflected in electricity, gas and water bills
- Reduction on energy subsidy costs
- Increase in number of green jobs
- Access to clean energy services
- Human and institutional capacity building through training, courses & talks
- Improved Health of living spaces
- Enhances community-based indigenous forestry
- Reduction of Carbon-foot Print as an asset for grass-root stake holders through Green-Carbon Card

Therefore RBI says "Green banking can be an avenue to reduce pollution and save the environment aiding sustainable economic growth."³

9. CONCLUSION:

As the carbon-credit might affect the rate return of banks in the long-run, now the banks in national and international level pro-actively playing role to take environmental and ecological aspects as part of their lending principle to go green. If the Carbon-Credit Co-Operative Banking (NCCB) is institutionalized and implemented sincerely, it would be act as an effective catalyst to GHG reduction to developing country like India. So the time has come for mass mobilization and to take some major steps to gradually adhere to the establishment of NCCB for a remarkable footprint to Indian Green Economy.

² 'Obama backs India's solar goals, seeks support for climate talks', REUTERS, Jan 25, 2015, <http://in.reuters.com/article/2015/01/25/india-obama-climatechange-idINKBN0KY0QN20150125>

³ Green Banking Framework 2013, Institute of Development and Research in Banking Technology (IDRBT), Established by Reserve Bank of India Page 20

10. REFERENCES:

1. The India Community Protocol for Accounting & Reporting Greenhouse Gas Emissions (ICP), PUBLIC COMMENT DRAFT, Version 1.1 – December 2012, ICLEI- Local Governments for Sustainability, South Asia, http://southasia.iclei.org/fileadmin/user_upload/documents/IPC.pdf
2. SMFG (Sumitomo Mitsui Financial Group), www.smfg.co.jp/english
3. Plant a Tree Today Foundation, PATT, <http://www.pattfoundation.org/>
4. Green Banking Framework 2013, Institute of Development and Research in Banking Technology (IDRBT), Established by Reserve Bank of India
5. IT VISION OF RESERVE BANK OF INDIA 2011-2017, Page No 11, <http://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/PublicationReport/PDFs/ITVSD220211.pdf>
6. 'Obama backs India's solar goals, seeks support for climate talks', REUTERS, Jan 25, 2015, <http://in.reuters.com/article/2015/01/25/india-obama-climatechange-idINKBN0KY0QN20150125>
7. A STUDY OF GREEN BANKING TRENDS IN INDIA, Dr. Nishikant Jha and Shraddha Bhome, International Monthly Refereed Journal of Research In Management & Technology127, ISSN – 2320-0073 Volume II, May'13, http://www.abhinavjournal.com/images/Management_&_Technology/May13/15.pdf
8. 'Green Banking practices in Bangladesh', Md. Shafiqul Islam, Prahallad Chandra Da, IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM) e-ISSN: 2278-487X. Volume 8, Issue 3 (Mar. - Apr. 2013), PP 39-44, <http://iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Vol8-issue3/G0833944.pdf>